

Morphological Study on Some Collected Species of Family Zingiberaceae in Bago Township

Aye Aye Mar^{*}, Ngwe Soe^{**}

Abstract

The specimens of family Zingiberaceae were collected in Bago Township from June to November in 2016, in order to study the morphological characters and uses. Plant samples were collected from five different areas (Day-Son-Par area, Kan-Taw-Gyi area, Sat-Inn area, Narani Sima area and Kyauk-Ta-Lone area). A total number of 8 individuals, belonging to 8 species in 5 genera of Zingiberaceae were collected, photographed and pressed as herbarium sheets. Then, the collected plants were identified, classified and their utilization was noted from the available literatures and also from the people living in these areas. In addition, locations were recorded with the GPS system. In this study, almost all plants in Zingiberaceae are found to be important natural resources for local villagers and mostly used as medicines, foods, drinks and ornamentals.

Introduction

Zingiberaceae comprises 53 genera and over 1200 species (Kress, 1990) and 50 genera and 1300 species (Te-Lin and Larsen, 2000). In Myanmar, the family Zingiberaceae comprises 25 genera and 159 species are recorded. Zingiberaceae family distributed in all States and Regions of Myanmar, however, many species are found abundantly in Bago, Mandalay, Taninthayi, Sagaing Regions and Kachin, Kayah, Kayin, Mon, Rachine and Shan State. Members of the Zingiberaceae are usually aromatic in all or least one of their plant parts. Thus species belong to this family are important natural sources of spices, herbal medicines, natural dyes, perfumes and multipurpose aesthetic compounds (Siriruga, 1999). The objectives of this study to identify the morphological characters of the collected specimens of the family Zingiberaceae and to give the information for utilization of this specimens

Materials and Methods

This study focused on Bago Township to collect the Zingiberaceous plants. The plants were collected from five sites of Bago Township, Day-Son-Pa area, Sat-Inn area, Kan-Taw-Gyi area, Narani Sima, and Kyauk-Ta-Lone area, during July to October in 2016. The collected fresh specimens were photographed. Each collected specimen of the selected species was pressed, dried and mounted on the herbarium sheet. The vegetative and floral parts of all the species were identified according to the references of Hooker (1894), Hundley and Chit Ko Ko (1987), Baker (1968), John Kress W. *et al* and Ceylon Vol. IV (M.D. Dassanayake, 1983).

Results

ScientificName - *Boesenbergia longiflora* (Wallich.) Kuntze.

English Name - Rosy Orchid Ginger

Myanmar Name- Seik-Phoo-Ni or Seik-Phoo-Chin

Perennial herbs, leafy shoot 30-45 cm in height. Rhizomes globose, tuberous roots finger-like, externally brown and internally pale yellow, ends of tuberous roots is globose. Leaf sheath is green to reddish green, striated, deeply channeled, glabrous; ligules bilobed, triangular, whitish green, glabrous; petioles pale green, glabrous; leaf blades elliptic to oblong

* Lecturer, Department of Botany, Bago University

** Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Botany, Pyay University

lanceolate, the bases rounded, slightly oblique, the margins entire, undulate, the tips acute to acuminate, the upper surface pale green, the lower reddish brown to dark green, both surfaces glabrous. Inflorescence spike, arise from the rhizome, basal sheath reddish, glabrous. Flowers white; bracts linear lanceolate, whitish green, silky, glabrous; bracteoles linear lanceolate, white, membranous, glabrous, calyx tubular, apex bifid, white, glabrous; corolla tubes white, glabrous; corolla lobes oblong, white, the posterior lobes larger than the lateral ones, glabrous. The lateral staminodes broadly obovate, pale yellow, apex rounded, connected to the labellum, glabrous; the labellum saccate, semi-orbicular, white, light yellow throat centre dark red, the apex elongate, red, emarginated, margin wrinkled revolute on the side, Fertile stamen one, the anther white, reflexed apical crest, the filament very short, pale yellow. Ovary sub-globose, white, tri-locular, axile placentation, 3 rows of ovules in each locule, glabrous; the styles filiform, white, the stigmas rounded, white. Fruits are not seen.

Uses : In the treatment of inflammatory bowel disease, ulcerative, colitis, aphthous ulcer and abscess.

Scientific Name - *Curcuma roscoeana* Wall.

English Name - Jewel of Burma

Myanmar Name- Marlar Ni, Taw-sanwin

Perennial herbs, pseudostems up to 70cm in height. Rhizomes oblongoid, light brown externally, creamy-yellowish inside, with small ovate tubers. Leaves sheaths pale green, pubescent; ligules bilobed, greenish translucent, hairy on the margin; petioles streaked pale green, pubescent; leaf blades oblong-ovate, the bases rounded, the margins entire, undulate, the tips aristate, both surfaces glabrous. Inflorescences spike, oblongoid, arise from the centre of a leafy tuft; peduncles long, green, glabrous; hidden within the pseudostem; flowers yellow; bracts numerous, ovate-spatulate, deep orange-red, coma bracts similar in color and size to fertile bracts, lower half forming deep funnel-shaped pouches subtending cincinnus of 2-4 flowered, upper part spreading, pubescent; bracteoles lanceolate, creamy white, glabrous; calyx 3-toothed, translucent white, unilaterally split, glabrous; corolla tubes, funnel, golden yellow, glabrous; corolla lobes ovate, creamy white, the posterior one larger and more concave, glabrous, Lateral staminodes unequally rhomboid, golden yellow; the labellum orbicular, golden yellow, emarginated, deeply yellow and thick in the centre, thinner lateral ones overlap the staminodes. Fertile stamen one, the filament sub-sessile, the anthers white, with basal spur. Ovary oblongoid, trilocular, 2 rows of ovules in each locule, axile placentation pubescent; the styles filiform, the stigmas passing between the anther sacs. Fruits globose.

Uses : Jewel of Myanmar is cultivated as a potted plant and also for flower.

Scientific Name - *Globba sessiliflora* L.

English Name - Stalkless swam flower

Myanmar Name- Waso

Perennial herbs, leafy shoot slender, about 70 cm in height. Rhizomes small, white, cylindrical. Leaf sheaths whitish green to reddish green, sparsely pubescent; ligules bipartite, membranous, densely pubescent; petioles absent; leaf blades oblong-lanceolate, the base cuneate, the margins entire, the tips acuminate, upper surfaces sparsely pubescent, lower densely pubescent. Inflorescences raceme, terminal, erect, many flowered. Flowers bright yellow, pedicellate, bracts ovate, greenish yellow; bulbils oblong, white, arise from the axils of bract; calyx 3, truncate, greenish to yellowish green; pubescent; corolla tubes yellow, densely pubescent; corolla lobes concave, lower middle portion minutely pubescent. The lateral staminodes linear, tips acuminate, yellow, outer surface pubescent; the labellum yellow, linear,

tips bifid, connate to the filament in a slender tube above the staminodes. Fertile stamen one, filament slender, white, the anthers without appendages. Ovary globose, unilocular, parietal placentation, many ovules in the locule, the style filiform, exerted from the anther lobes, the stigma hairy. Fruits globose to ovoid, slightly warted. Seeds ovoid, hairy.

Uses : The flowers are used in religious ceremony.

Scientific Name - *Kaempferia rotunda* L.

English Name - Resurrection lily

Myanmar Name- Myay-pa-dauk

Perennial herbs, leafy shoot 30-40 cm in height, green above and greenish brown below. Rhizomes oblongoid or globose, creamy white externally, white inside, tuberous roots spindle-shaped. Leaf sheaths greenish brown to reddish purple, pubescent; ligules bilobed, triangular, green to brownish green, membranous, pubescent; petioles reddish purple to purplish brown, pubescent; leaf blades broadly elliptic to oblanceolate, green above with two rows of silver spots, reddish brown beneath, the bases attenuate, the margins entire, undulate, the tips acute to acuminate, pubescent. Inflorescences scapose, spicate cymes; peduncles white or pale green, glabrous. Flowers purple; bracts greenish brown, overlap the peduncle, pubescent; bracteoles lanceolate, brownish green with purplish lines, pubescent; calyx tubular, greenish white below, pinkish green above, glabrous; corolla tubes cylindrical, slightly curved, white, glabrous; corolla lobes lanceolate to broadly lanceolate, concave, white, membranous. The lateral staminodes oblong, the tips shallowly emarginated, crisped, white; the labellum oblong, deeply bilobed, lilac with white margin. Fertile stamen one, the anther white, anther crest obovate, purple, bilobed, the filament very short. Ovary oblongoid, tri-locular, axile placentation, one row of ovules in each locule, tomentose, the styles filiform, pubescent; the stigma funnel-shaped. Fruits are not seen.

Uses : The tuber is used to treat abdominal illness, gastric complaints. The rhizome is used to treat stomachache. The leaves are used as body lotion.

Scientific Name - *Zingiber pandurata* Roxb.

English Name - Not-Known

Myanmar Name- Taw-tha-lin-phoo

Perennial herbs, pseudostem up to 120 cm in height. Rhizomes thick, horizontal, externally pinkish brown and internally pale yellow. Leaf sheaths green to reddish brown, glabrous; ligules bipartite, rounded, pale green, membranous, pubescent, petioles absent; leaf blades oblong-lanceolate, the bases cuneate, the margins entire, undulate, the tips acute to acuminate, the upper surface glabrous, both lower surface and the midrib pubescent. Inflorescences spike, oblong, dense-head, arise from the rhizomes; peduncles long, cylindrical, reddish green. Flowers red; the bracts ovate, the tips acute, red, glabrous; bracteoles ovate-lanceolate, white, the tips red, glabrous; calyx 3-lobed, tubular; calyx lobes red, glabrous; corolla tubes pinkish white, glabrous; corolla lobes ovate-lanceolate, red, the posterior lobes large, glabrous. The labellum obovate, yellowish-white, unspotted, not emarginated. Fertile stamen one, the anthers reddish yellow, the filaments very short, the anther crest yellow. Ovary oblongoid, white, tri-locular, axile placentation, 2 rows of ovules in each locule, sparsely pubescent; the styles filiform, the stigmas white, passing between the anther sacs. Fruits are not seen.

Uses : The inflorescences and flowers are used as vegetables.

Scientific Name - *Zingiber zerumbet* (L.) Smith.

English Name - Bitter ginger

Myanmar Name- Linne-gyi

Perennial herbs, pseudostems about 120 cm in height. Rhizomes tuberous, aromatic, externally light brown and internally light yellow. Leaf sheaths green, slightly pubescent; ligules bifid, lobes rounded, pale green, membranous, sparsely pubescent; petioles pale green, pubescent; leaf blades oblong-lanceolate, the bases cuneate, the margins entire, undulate, the tips acute to acuminate, midribs and both surfaces pubescent. Inflorescences cone-like spike, ovate-oblong, arise from the underground rhizomes; peduncles long, green, glabrous. Flowers yellowish white; the bracts ovate, the tips rounded, initially green and gradually changed into red at mature, glabrous; bracteoles linear lanceolate, white, glabrous; calyx 3-lobed, tubular; white; membranous, unilaterally split; corolla tubes yellowish white, glabrous; corolla lobes lanceolates, yellowish white, the posterior lobes largest, the outer one narrower. The labellum obovate, yellowish-white, the central lobes emarginated, glabrous. Fertile stamen one, the anthers elliptic-oblong, yellowish white, the anther crest curved. Ovary globose, white, tri-locular, axile placentation, many ovules in each locule, glabrous; the style filiform, the stigma white, passing between the anther sacs. Fruits obovoid, red, capsule.

Uses : The inflorescences and flowers are used as vegetable for diarrhea and dysentery.

Scientific Name - *Zingiber squarroum* (Roxb.)

English Name - Ginger

Myanmar Name- Tauk-ta

Perennial herbs, pseudostems up to 200 cm in height. Rhizomes thick, tuberous roots, oval-shaped. Leaf sheaths green, glabrous; ligules bifid, lobes rounded, pale green, membranous, sparsely pubescent, petioles very short, pale green or red, glabrous; leaf blades oblong-lanceolate, the bases attenuate, the margins entire, undulate, the tips acute to acuminate, upper surfaces glabrous, the lower pubescent. Inflorescences dense globose head, arising from the rhizomes, peduncles very short. Flowers purplish white; the bracts narrowly lanceolate, tips hooked, greenish red, pubescent; bracteoles obtuse, greenish red, pubescent; calyx 3-lobed, tubular; pale green with red striated, unilaterally split, pubescent; corolla tubes pinkish white, narrowly funnel-shaped; glabrous; corolla lobes ovate-lanceolate, pinkish white. The labellum, ovate, emarginated, purple with white spots, the tips lilac, glabrous. Fertile stamen one, the anther connective problonged into an elongated dark-red crest which embraces the curved upper part of the style. Ovary globose, white, tri-locular, axile placentation, many ovules in each locule, pubescent; the styles filiform, the stigmas turbinate. Fruits oblong, septicial capsule, reddish green to red. Seeds black.

Uses : Fruits are used as salad and rhizomes are used for diarrhea.

Scientific Name - *Zingiber barbatum* sp.

English Name - Wild-ginger

Myanmar Name- Meik-Thalin

Perennial herbs, pseudostems about 160 cm in height. Rhizomes thick, tuberous roots with fusiform tubers at tips; leaf sheaths reddish brown, longitudinal striated, pililopse; ligules bi-lobed, triangular, pale brown, pilose; petioles absent; leaf blades oblong-lanceolate, the bases cuneate, the margins entire, undulate, the tips acute to acuminate, both surfaces dense pilose, midrib and margins also. Inflorescences dense head, spike, oblong, arising from

rhizomes, dense pilose; peduncles reddish green, dense pilose. Flowers white; bracts ovate-lanceolate, brownish green, pilose; bracteoles oblong-lanceolate, pinkish red, pilose; calyx 3-lobed, tubular; white, unilaterally split, glabrous; corolla tubes white, glabrous; corolla lobes ovate-lanceolate, white, glabrous. The labellum yellowish white, obovate, glabrous. Fertile stamen one, the anther white, connective prolonged into an white elongated crest. Ovary globose, white, tri-loculars, axile placentation, many ovules in each locule, puberulous; style filiform, the stigmas turbinate. Fruits are not seen.

Uses : Dysentery, skin diseases, antidote for snake venom and indigestion.

Discussion and Conclusion

8 specimens were collected from the five study area of Bago Township during the flowering period of June to November in 2016. The total of 8 species with 5 genera have been identified. The genus *Boesenbergia* is characterized by inflorescence terminal bearing 2-ranked bracts. Each bract subtended single boat-shaped bracteole and flower. The flowers have a saccate labellum. The genus *Curcuma* is characterized by bracts connate for half their length and forming pouches, spreading at the free ends, apical bracts often differently coloured, large, sterile bracts forming a coma. Filament short, anther with basal spur. The genus *Globba* is easily distinguished by having flower with lip joined to the stamen and long exerted, curved stamen. The anther with or without one or two triangular appendages, ovary one locule, parietal placentation. The genus *Kaempferia* is easily distinguished by roots bearing small tubers. Pseudostem short; leaf blade suborbicular. Inflorescences scapose cyme. The lateral staminodes suborbicular. Labellum obovate, spreading fan-like. The anther crest ovate, filling throat of corolla tube. The genus *Zingiber* is characterized by having pulvinous petiole, lateral staminodes adnate to the labellum, forming a three lobed labellum; central lobe cleft apex, filament short and anther crest wrapped around the exerted style. In this study, most genera are widely used by villagers as a local application to relieve stomachache, tonic, colic, dysentery, carminative, rheumatism, diarrhea. Moreover, these plants are also used as spices and vegetables. Therefore, these plants should be further investigated for its medicinal values due to its abundant occurrence and used by local people in Bago Township.

Acknowledgements

I acknowledge my great gratitude to Dr. Aye Aye Tun, Rector and Dr. Yin Yin Than, Pro-Rector, Bago University, for their permission to conduct this paper. I am also grateful to Professor Dr. San Wai Aung, Head of Department of Botany, Bago University and Professor Dr. Tin Moe Aye, Department of Botany, Bago University.

References

- Backer, C. A. and R.C. Bakhuizen Van Den Brink (1968). *Flora of Java, Vol. III, N.V.P, Noordhoff Groninger*. The Netherlands.
- Dassanayake M.D. (1987). *A revised Hand Book to the Flora of Ceylon Vol. IV*
- Hooker. J. D (1849). *The Flora of British India. Vol. VI*. L. REEVE & Co. Ltd., London.
- Hundley. H. G. and Chit Ko Ko, (1987). *List of Trees, Shrubs, Herbs and Principle Climbers* etc., Govt Printing and State, Union of Burma, Rangoon.
- John Kress W, Robert A. Defilipps, Ellen Farr and Daw Yin Yin Kyi (2003). *A checklish of the Trees, Shrubs, Herbs and Climbers of Myanmar*.
- Larsen K, Ibrahim H, Khaw SH, saw LG (1999). In: Wong KM (Ed) *Gingers of Peninsular Malaysia and Singapore*, Natural History Publications, Borneo, pp 1-92.
- Siriruga P (1999). *Thai Zingiberaceae: species diversity and their uses*. <http://www.iupac.org/symposia/proceedings/Phuket97/Siriruga.html>
- Te-Lin W, Larsen K (2000). *Zingiberaceae. Flora of China 24, 322-377*.

Boesenbergia longiflora (Wallich.) Kuntze.

Habit

Inflorescence

Flower

Curcuma roscoeana Wall.

Habit

Inflorescence

Inflorescence

Globba sessiliflora Sims.

Habit

Inflorescence

Kaempferia rotunda L.

Habit

Flower

Zingiber panduratum Roxb.

Habit

Inflorescence

Zingiber zerumbet (L.) Roscoe ex J.E. Sm.

Habit

Inflorescence

Zingiber squarrosum Roxb.

Habit

Inflorescence

Zingiber barbatum Wall.

Habit

Inflorescence